

THE NOTIONAL CONSTITUENT OF CONCEPT DEATH/ЎЛИМ/ӨЛИМ

Ganieva Zuxra Muratbaevna

Linguistics (English) PhD student at Karakalpak State University

Abstract: The article discusses the comparative analysis of the notional constituent of the concept Death in the English, Uzbek, and Karakalpak languages. The study of the representation of the concept Death was conducted using lexicographic data found in the explanatory dictionaries of the English, Uzbek, and Karakalpak languages. The analysis revealed that despite being a concept that exists in all languages and cultures, the representation of the concept of Death varies across different linguacultures. The study revealed that the understanding of the concept Death primarily revolves around its biological aspect (Death – the end of life, the state of being dead or killed, the cause of end of life). Also, in many linguacultures Death can be personified and symbolized as a skeleton carrying a scythe in art and literature. Moreover, Death can be not only the end of life but a thing or action as well. The concept Death has the following synonyms in the given languages: **death** – decease, demise, passing; **ЎЛИМ** – вафот, қазо; **ӨЛИМ** – эжел, муғаллақ, паймана;

Key words: concept death, definition, notional constituent, synonym.

The concept is a fundamental idea in the fields of philosophy of language, cognitive linguistics, linguoculturology, linguoconceptology, and other linguistic domains that examine the role of human in language. These fields focus on the anthropocentric paradigm of language learning. From a cognitive linguistics perspective: “a concept is a term that serves to explain the units of mental or psychic resources of our consciousness and the information structure that reflects human knowledge and experience; operational content unit of memory, mental lexicon, conceptual system and language of the brain (*lingua mentalis*), the whole picture of the world, reflected in the human psyche” [3, p. 90]. The essence of this definition comes down to the fact that a concept is a mental unit that captures human knowledge

and contributes to knowledge of the world, that is, it is both a product and a tool of knowledge. Z.D. Popova and I. A. Sternin provides similar definition by saying that concept is “global mental a unit that represents a quantum of structured knowledge” [4, p. 4].

One of the important tasks in the theory of a concept is the study of its structure. Most researchers (Yu. S. Stepanov, S. G. Vorkachev, V.I. Karasik, G.G. Slyshkin and etc.) note the three-component structure of the concept. Based on extensive research, scientists are convinced that a concept includes a number of various elements, known as conceptual characteristics, which are perceived differently in consciousness and vary in their level of abstraction. The concept possesses a unique characteristic in its structure, wherein it is composed of multiple layers that have been shaped by the cultural developments of various historical periods. Therefore, the concept is comprised of distinct layers that have evolved over time, each with its own unique formation, origin, and meaning, so according to Yu. S. Stepanov, concept has the following layers: 1) primary (present); 2) additional (inactive, past); 3) internal (often subconscious) structure [5, p. 46-48]. Similar viewpoint has S. G. Vorkachev, who also identifies three components in the concept: a) conceptual, consisting of conceptual features and definitional structure; b) figurative, formed with the help of cognitive metaphors that support the concept in the minds of speakers of a particular language and c) meaningful, including etymological, associative, paradigmatic, syntagmatic characteristics of a concept that determine its place in the lexicogrammatical system of a particular language [1, p. 7]. V.I. Karasik and G.G. Slyshkin note the presence of: a) conceptual (informational and factual); b) figurative (cognitively metaphorical); c) value (evaluative, normative) components. This is due, according to researchers, to the fact that, unlike other mental units (frame, script, concept, script, gestalt, etc.), in the concept the axiological element is emphasized, because “the center of the concept is always value” [2, p. 75–80].

The following study is based on the above-mentioned structure of the concept to identify the notional constituent of the given concept **Death**. Firstly, it is working with thesaurus to find out diverse interpretations of the concept **Death**, the other part

of the research is connected with the synonyms of the given concept. The analysis focuses on the lexemes **Death/Ўлим/Олим**, which also serve as the names of the concept. The analysis is conducted using the following dictionaries and thesaurus CALD, CIDE, LDCE, MWALD, ODCE, CD, WNDS, ЎТИЛ, ЎТСКИЛ, ҚҚТС, ҚТСКҚС pertaining to the specified languages. The study findings indicate that the concept **Death** in given languages is primarily understood as a biological phenomenon which is available in all three languages under comparison.

1. The end of life:

- the end of life (CIDE); (CALD); - the end of life of a person or animal (LDCE); – the ending of a particular person’s life (MWALD); - the end of life: the time when someone or something dies; – the permanent end of something that is not alive (MWALD); - the end of life; time or manner of dying (LDCE); – the permanent end of all functions of life in an organism or some of its cellular components (CD); – the permanent cessation of all vital functions in a plant or animal (MCD); - Инсон ёки ҳайвон ҳаётининг тўхташи; вафот, қазо (ЎТИЛ); - Организм ҳаёт фаолиятининг бутунлай тўхташи, тугаши; ортга қайтмас жараён, ҳужайра ва тўқималарда физиологик жараёнлар тўхтаб, ортга қайтмас ҳолат содир бўлиши (ЎТИЛ); - Эжел, қаза (КТТС);

- irreversible ending of life; dying or being killed (ODCE);

The initial subset of lexical interpretations of the concept **Death** portrays it as primarily a biological phenomenon which is observed in all three languages of the research. Moreover, it is crucial to note that both English and Uzbek thesauruses also define it as an irreversible process (irreversible ending of life/ ортга қайтмас жараён/ ортга қайтмас ҳолат). Multiple dictionaries and thesauruses define death as the termination of life for a person, animal, or plant, emphasizing the biological process of dying as the cessation of all vital functions (the permanent end of all functions of life in an organism). Nevertheless, there exist certain representations under which the notion of death can be understood as a permanent termination, encompassing both the concept of time and the manner of dying (the time when

someone or something dies/ хужайра ва тўқималарда физиологик жараёнлар тўхтаб, ортга қайтмас ҳолат содир бўлиши).

2. the state of being dead or killed;

- being dead (ODCE); - the state of being dead (LDCE); - state or condition of being dead (MCD); -the action or fact of dying or being killed, an instance of person or animal dying (CODCE); - жон таслим қилиш, жон бериш жараёни, вақти, ўлим юз бериши ва у билан боғлиқ ҳолат, шароит, жараён. (ЎТИЛ);

The following interpretation of the concept **Death** as a state of being dead has been detected only in English and Uzbek thesauruses, but it is vital to state that the elucidations gathered from both languages slightly differentiate. In English thesauruses, for example, the concept of being dead has been defined by emphasizing the notion that individuals might enter this state by both natural and non-natural means, such as being deliberately killed by another entity (the action or fact of dying or being killed). However, this specific interpretation in Uzbek is identified by emphasizing death more as a process that has its time and a suitable condition to occur (жон таслим қилиш, жон бериш жараёни, вақти, ўлим юз бериши ва у билан боғлиқ ҳолат, шароит, жараён).

Finding an interpretation that isn't comparable in other languages under comparison is quite interesting. The next interpretation is exclusively found in English and attributes death as both the cause and origin of the cessation of life.

•the cause of end of life;

- the cause of dying (MCD);
- the cause of loss of life (LDCE);
- a cause or source of death (CD);

The subsequent subgroup, also exclusively presented in English, pertains to the symbolism of death, depicted as a human, skeleton, or beast wielding a scythe that possesses the ability and strength to terminate life. Such symbolism is predominantly portrayed in literary works and art mostly.

•the symbolism of death;

- (Death) the personification of the power that destroys life, often represented as a skeleton or an old man holding a scythe (CODCE); - the personification of death esp. as a skeleton (ODCE); - a personification of death, usually a skeleton or an old man holding a scythe (CD); - (Death) figure thought of as representing death, usually symbolized by a skeleton carrying a scythe (MCD);

- (Death) the force that ends life and is often shown in an art or literature as a skeleton - *Death could be seen lurking in the corner of the painting.*

- *When Death comes to take me away* (MWALD); - the destroyer of life usually represented as a skeleton (LDCE);

- Death a creature that looks like a human skeleton, used in paintings, stories etc. to represent the fact that people die - *A picture of Death wearing a black cloak and holding a sickle* (LDCE);

The following meaning, again solely found in English thesauruses, death is defined as the annihilation of something or the termination of a particular course of acts.

•**death is destruction;**

- the destruction or end of something (CODCE); - ending or destruction of anything, extinction (MCD); - destruction or disappearance - *A defeat that meant the death of all my hopes; Death to imperialism! These regulations could spell the death of the American car industry* (LDCE); - destruction: ending (ODCE); - termination or destruction (CD);

In addition to the aforementioned meanings of death in English, there is one additional meaning that should be emphasized. For instance, the phrase *martyr's death* refers to the manner in which someone dies, but it also carries a religious connotation. In this context, a martyr is defined as a person who is killed for their testimony or faith in Jesus, and this type of death typically involves methods such as sawing, stoning, crucifixion, burning at the stake, or other forms of torture (wikipedia.com). This concept of martyrdom is particularly associated with Christianity, Islam (CALD); Such concept also exists in Uzbek as “шаҳид” - дин ёки мазҳаб йўлида ва б. айрим (ҳадисларда белгиланган) ҳолатларда ҳалок бўлган

шахс. [Салоҳиддин:] *Жангда ўлган — шахид, ўлдирган — ғозий, буни муслмонларга айтиши керак.* (Н. Сафаров, Шарқ тонги).

The research of the synonyms of concept **Death** has been conducted in all three indicated languages and revealed the following synonyms: the lexeme **death** in English has 3 synonyms: *decease* - mostly applied to human beings except figurative meaning, especially used in legal context but in ordinary use contain slightly euphemistic and rhetorical quality, *demise*- applied only to human beings except figurative use, legal context, in literal use has become somewhat pompous or affected – *The lady’s demise had been ascribed to apoplexy* – Hynd; *passing* – an euphemism for the death of a person [WNDS]. Besides, there are many idiomatic expressions that can be used as synonyms: *the last debt (inf), the long sleep (inf), the big sleep (inf), end of life, loss of life, close of life/existence, close one’s eyes, depart this life* and etc.

- Upon your decease the house will pass to your wife.

- Upon his demise the title will pass on his son.

- The demise of a famous newspaper (fig).

- All that live must die, passing through nature to eternity. (W.Shakespeare)

[LDCE];

In Uzbek language the lexeme ўлим has 2 synonyms, among them the lexeme ўлим itself is considered as the general and widely used word, *вафот* – is mostly used in literature works, *қазо* – is used rarely and mostly with the verb йетмоқ (қазо йетмоқ) [ЎТСКИЛ]; Furthermore, the following phrases also can be considered as synonyms: *ажал(и) йетмоқ, асфаласофилинга (аспаласопилинга) кетмоқ, бандалик қилмоқ (бандаликни бажо келтирмоқ), дунё билан видолашмоқ, энгак ташламоқ, жаҳондан кетмоқ, жон тарк этмоқ, оёғ(и)ни узатмоқ* and etc;

- “Гумондор борми?” – деди уста. “Гумондор-ку йуқ, аммо бечоранинг ўлими жуда қизиқ кунга тўғри келди”. (А.Қодирий, Ўткан кунлар).

- Гулнор қиз Унсин билан гаплашганда, унинг қишлоғи, уй-жой, тирикчиликлари, онаси, у бечора хотиннинг вафоти ва шунинг сингари нарсалари тўғрисида сўз очар еди. (Ойбек, Қутлуғ қон).

- **Sultonning qazosini falokat dema, taxt bo’sh qolganidan foydalanib, Sulton Abusaid Mirzo Xurosonga kirganini falokat de!** (I.Sulton, Alisher Navoiy) [ЎТСКИЛ];

In Karakalpak the lexeme **өлим** has 4 synonyms, here the lexemes *өлим* and *қаза* are also considered as general words that can be used both for human and animal’s death, *әжел* – is mostly used as a personification of death, *муғаллақ* – dying by falling from something or sudden death, *паймана* – actually when this word is used individually it means life, but when it used with verb *толды, толыў* (пайманасы толды, пайманасы толыў) it means somebody is suffered enough from this life and now ready to go to eternity. Aside from these, the below phrases can also be regarded as synonyms: *ақыретке жөнеў, гум болыў, деми таўсылыў, дуньядан өтиў, ялғанишыдан өтиў, жан тәслым етиў, жер тартыў, көз жумыў, көзине қум қуйылыў, қаза болыў* and so on;

- *Бийшараның өмири узақ болмады,*

Әжел аждархасы жутты жалмады. (А. Дабылов)

- *Зыяны жоқ. Муғаллақ деген аяқ астында.* (Т. Қайыпбергенов)

- *Пайманасы толды мекен,*

Қызыл гули солды мекен,

Ешек ҳадал болды мекен,

Ешек суннет еткен хожам. (Бердақ) [ҚТСКС];

To summarize, it is evident that the concept Death is universal and has connections to all lingucultures. The study focused on finding the notional constituent of the concept **Death**, and it revealed similarities as well as differences across three languages being examined. To the general characteristics can be considered the following interpretations such as: a) end of life, b) the state of being dead or killed; and for the differences: a) the cause of end of life, b) destruction of something, c) the symbolism of death; the analysis of synonyms showed that the lexeme death has the subsequent synonyms: **death** – decease, demise, passing; **ўлим** – вафот, қазо; **өлим** – әжел, муғаллақ, паймана;

References:

1. Воркачев С. Г. Постулаты лингвоконцептологии // Антология концептов. М.: Гнозис, 2007. С. 10-11.
2. Карасик В. И., Слышкин Г. Г. Лингвокультурный концепт как единица исследования // Методологические проблемы когнитивной лингвистики: Сб. науч. тр. Воронеж, 2001. С. 75-80.
3. Кубрякова Е.С. Концепт / // Краткий словарь когнитивных терминов. М.: Изд-во МГУ, 1996. - С. 90-93.
4. Попова, З.Д. Стернин И.А. Понятие «концепт» в лингвистических исследованиях. Воронеж: Изд-во ВГУ, 2000. – 30 с.
5. Степанов Ю. С. Константы: Словарь русской культуры, 2004. 992 с;